

Table 1. Plant traits of Zhenong 921.

Year	Duration (d)	Plants	Panicles	Productive tillers (%)	Plant height (cm)
		(no. m ²)			
1994	104.9	195.0	406.5	77.4	68.9
1995	112.8	156.0	339.0	76.6	73.8
1996	109.3	162.0	411.0	73.5	80.7
Mean	109.0	171.0	385.5	75.8	74.5

Table 2. Agronomic traits of Zhenong 921.

Year	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	Fertilized grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)
1994	17.4	85.9	64.3	74.9	27.6
1995	17.6	98.3	70.6	71.8	27.6
1996	18.3	88.3	75.0	84.9	27.2
Mean	17.8	90.8	70.0	77.2	27.5

respectively. It has 83.9% brown rice recovery, 75.5% milled rice recovery, 43.9% head milled rice recovery, 26.3% amylose content, 50 mm gel

consistency, an alkali spreading value of 3, and acceptable cooking or eating quality. ■

Cytogenetics of alien chromosome addition lines in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) with single chromosomes of *O. punctata* Kotschy

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Monosomic alien addition lines (MAALs) of *O. sativa* carrying single chromosomes of *O. punctata* were developed (Yasui and Iwata 1991). In the progenies of these MAALs, we identified plants in which the extra chromosome was telocentric or acrocentric.

Three monotelosomic alien addition lines (MtAALs) and one monoacrocentric alien addition line (MaAAL), each carrying single chromosomes of *O. punctata*, were isolated from the progenies of the respective MAALs for chromosomes 2, 4, 7, and 9. Mitotic and meiotic chromosomes of the MtAALs and an MaAAL were analyzed (see figure). A telosome as an extra chromosome was observed in the

respective MtAALs and one of them was for a short arm of chromosome 9. An acrocentric that consisted of a complete short arm and a heterochromatic proximal region of a long arm for chromosome 4 was observed in the MaAAL. Three MtAALs were

designated as MtAALs 2, 7, and 9S, respectively, and one MaAAL was designated as MaAAL 4S4L.

Morphology, seed fertility, and transmission of the extra chromosome of the MtAALs and the MaAAL were compared with the respective primary trisomics and MAALs. The plant morphology of MtAAL 2 and MaAAL 4S4L was similar to that of the respective MAALs, but that of MtAAL 9S was similar to disomics and that of MtAAL 7 was similar to secondary trisomics for the short arm of chromosome 7. Seed fertility of the MAAL, which ranged from 6.6% for MtAAL 2 to 94.5% for MtAAL 7, was higher than the respective primary trisomics and MAALs. The transmission rates of the extra chromosome, which ranged from 22.0% for MtAAL 2 to 28.2% for MaAAL 4S4L, were similar to those of the respective MAALs.

The mode of meiotic chromosome behavior of the MtAALs and the MaAAL was compared with that of the respective primary trisomics and MAALs (see table). The ratios of the pollen mother cells (PMCs) with a trivalent were clearly different between primary trisomics (32-67%) and

Comparison of meiotic chromosome behavior of primary trisomics and MAALs each with a single chromosome of *O. punctata*.

Trisomics/MAAL	Number of cells			Cells with trivalent (%)
	12II+11 11II+3I ^a	11II+1III	Total	
Triplo 2	45	21	66	31.8
MAAL 2	158	5	163	3.1
MtAAL 2	26	0	26	0
Triplo 4	31	62	93	66.7
MAAL 4	171	0	171	0
MaAAL 4S4L ^b	50	0	50	0
Triplo 7	47	83	130	63.9
MAAL 7	54	0	54	0
MtAAL 7	155	1	156	0.6
Triplo 9	25	51	76	67.1
MAAL 9	60	0	60	0
MtAAL 9S ^c	41	0	41	0

^aTwo PMCs of MtAAL 2 and three PMCs of MtAAL 7 showed 11II+3I. ^bMonoacrocentric alien addition line carrying the complete short arm and the proximal long arm of chromosome 4 derived from *O. punctata*. ^cMonotelosomic alien addition line carrying the short arm of chromosome 9 derived from *O. punctata*.

Chromosome constitution of three monotelosomic and one monoacrocentric alien addition lines of rice each carrying a telocentric or acrocentric single chromosome of *O. punctata*. Mitotic chromosomes of MtAAL 2 (a), MaAAL 4S4L (b), and MtAAL 7(c), and meiotic chromosomes of MtAAL 9S (d and e). Each arrow indicates the telocentric and/or acrocentric chromosomes derived from *O. punctata*.

MAALs or Mt(a)AALs (approximately 0%). The telocentric and acrocentric chromosomes would originate from a misdivision of an alien chromosome and the following chromosome breakage in the PMCs of the respective MAALs at the first or second anaphase. The addition lines with small chromosomal fragments such as alien telocentric and acrocentric chromosomes will serve as a source to transfer useful genes from wild relatives to cultivated rice.

Reference

Yasui H, Iwata N. 1991. Production of monosomic alien addition lines of *Oryza sativa* having a single *O. punctata* chromosome. In: Rice genetics II. Proceedings of the Second International Rice Genetics Symposium, 14-18 May 1990. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 147-155. ■

Genetic, histological, and histochemical evidence for reversion to partial fertility in WA CMS line IR54752A

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The widely used wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line IR54752A for the hybrid rice program at IRRI and in India was reported to be unstable for male sterility characters and therefore restricted to use in seed production. We investigated the causes for the breakdown in sterility. All evidence gathered suggested the presence of multiple nuclear genes (minor) for fertility in the CMS line. Evidence included the presence of partially fertile plants in a cross with the isonuclear maintainer line, genetic studies using selfed and test-crossed progenies of the partially fertile plants, and the comparative ease of restoration of fertility of this CMS line in crosses with restorers

as well as maintainer lines of other CMS lines belonging to the same cytoplasmic source. Histological studies revealed normal behavior and functioning of anther wall tissues, including tapetum and endothecium, as well as normal development of microspores in CMS line IR54752A up to the liberation of microspores. The CMS pollen grains differed from other fertile pollen in histochemical components such as starch, proteins, and RNA at maturity, indicating that mobilization of metabolites to the pollen grains was hindered to some extent at maturity. This showed that factors within the microspore were responsible for the breakdown in sterility in IR54752A. ■

Genetics of the thermosensitive genic male sterility trait in rice

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UPRI 95-140 (P1), the thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) line of low-temperature fertility transformation type, was analyzed for its inheritance and transformation behavior. Parents, F_1 , F_2 , and six test crosses between TGMS (female parent) and UPR1 95-141 (P2), UPR1 95-165 (P3), UPR1 95-124 (P4), UPR1 95-117 (P5), and IR36 (P6)

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.